

Myth Mapping Stanton Drew through Multisensory Engagements

Introduction

A persistent tension continues to run through landscape archaeology: between formalised, often technologically mediated spatial analysis, and the subjective, embodied experiences of being-in-place. While tools such as GIS, magnetometry, digital modelling, and other remote sensing techniques can provide structural insights, they are often situated within Cartesian, ocularcentric paradigms that privilege the measurable over the affective and atmospheric (Landeschi & Betts, 2023). Yet recent work in digitally mediated sensory archaeology suggests these two strands (the experiential and the computational) need not be at odds but entangled in the interpretive process (Eve & Gillings, 2023). This project responds to that possibility by exploring Stanton Drew through an embodied and reflexive approach: a phenomenological walk grounded in soft phenomenology (Hamilton et al., 2006), where geophysical readings and digital reconstructions served not as empirical constraints, but as imaginative catalysts.

From this emerged a myth map, as a response that moves past cartographic representation, giving form to the atmospheric, animistic, and more-than-human presences that shaped my experience. The aim of this project was not to reconstruct Stanton Drew's prehistoric reality, but to examine how alternative modes of knowing, grounded in listening, movement, and felt relation, might offer insight into the site's affective and temporal complexity. In doing so, it contributes to wider debates on the role of subjectivity, creativity, and multisensory engagement within archaeological practice. Through walking, dwelling, and mapping differently, this study reconsiders what it means to encounter a landscape, not as passive observer, but as co-participant in its ongoing becoming.

Background

Despite being home to the second-largest stone circle in Britain, the site has often lingered at the periphery of archaeological attention (English Heritage, n.d). Its status as a Scheduled Monument affirms its significance, yet compared to Stonehenge or Avebury, Stanton Drew has been less frequently excavated, modelled, or reinscribed into dominant archaeological narratives. The site comprises three main stone circles: the Great Circle, North East Circle, and South West Circle, as well as avenues, the Cove, Hautville's Quoit, and other dispersed stones. However, this catalogue of features only partially accounts for its presence. Magnetometry surveys in the late 1990s and early 2000s (David et al., 2004; Oswin et al., 2009, 2011) revealed buried timber structures and concentric postholes beneath the surface (*Fig 1*), while further work around the River Chew identified additional sub-surface anomalies (Richards et al., 2012; Simmonds et al., 2015). These findings

deepen rather than resolve the site's mystery, extending its significance beyond what can be seen, and invites our attention to what lies beneath, between, or beyond.

Figure 1. Magnetometry reading focused on the Great Circle, with partial readings of the surrounding landscape, including the North East Circle (Oswald et al., 2009).

From 2000 to 2005, Dr Lewis's *Stanton Drew Environs Project* undertook fieldwalking, augering, and test pitting in several fields, including excavation of a buried stone at Church Farm and a field east of the South West Circle (cited in Oswald, 2017: 2). Further work in 2009 of land at Church Farm, around 500 metres south of the current monument complex, was prompted by development plans and geophysical anomalies (cited in Oswald, 2017: 2). Evaluation by Avon Archaeological Unit Ltd revealed features including a postmedieval field boundary, a backfilled pond, and several intercutting gullies. Finds included worked flints, medieval pottery, Romano-British ceramics dating to the 3rd-4th centuries AD, and evidence of metalworking (cited in Oswald, 2017: 2). While archaeologically significant, these remains relate to later periods and lie beyond the megalithic core of Stanton Drew. Yet despite their distances in time, encountering this knowledge prior to my walk influenced how I traversed and perceived the accumulated layers of human presence. This complexity challenged any singular reading of the landscape and extended the reflexive texture of this project, a reminder that archaeological meaning is not confined to monumentality alone.

Methodology and its Affordances

This project explored Stanton Drew through multiple spatial lenses that included quantitative, qualitative, experiential and creative approaches. While my phenomenological walk drew initial influence from Tilley's (1994) foundational work on landscape phenomenology, particularly his emphasis on bodily movement, visual encounter, and spatial perception, I adopted a softer phenomenology, as proposed by Hamilton et al. (2006). Their framework, which encourages methodological transparency, reflexivity, and the integration of both traditional and digital approaches, afforded comprehensive value to this project. While Tilley critiques representational tools such as maps and aerial photography for producing a detached, 'bird's-eye view', that renders the viewer outside of the experience (Tilley 1994: 21), my incorporation of technological models, specifically magnetometry readings and digital reconstructions (**Figures 1 & 2**), did not result in detachment. Instead, they became generative tools within an embodied and sensorial methodology.

This project did not follow a fixed methodological script, but unfolded as an emergent, embodied relation with place. Through the notion of *soft phenomenology*, I approached the landscape not through pre-formulated hypotheses, but through a sensorial openness to how space, sound, memory, and both material presence and absence might coalesce in situ (Csordas, 2002). In this spirit, I engaged Stanton Drew through a slow, attentive walk that resisted linearity or repetition. This was not about surveying or mapping in any conventional sense; rather, it was about surrendering to the site's rhythms, a method of moving *with* rather than moving *through* (Wunderlich, 2008), and attuning to the affective forces that linger, circulate, and intensify across environments (McCormack, 2007).

Figure 2. The Great Circle with timber posts, a digital reconstruction (Rothwell, 2013).

In response, I developed a myth map: an experiential, interpretive composition - assisted by my field notes - that sought to give form to the resonances, disjunctions, and emotional currents encountered (**Fig 3**). As Feld (1996: 91) writes in his acoustemological study of the Kaluli, "as places make sense, senses make place." At the Druids Arms pub, this mutual shaping of perception and place was articulated not through vision or touch,

but through sound. Seated inside for over thirty minutes, I closed my eyes and listened. What followed was not a passive auditory reception, but a concentrated, affective experience of place as reverence. Composed of voices in conversation, the soundscape was not backgrounding noise, but rather, a tonal ecology modulating like an ambient chorus, carrying a semiotic charge. In this moment of listening, one voice emerged from the many, not in words, but as an intonation that something was still being honoured here. However, by *dwelling* in place, as advocated by Ingold (2007), my experiences at Stanton Drew revealed that sound was only one element of ‘listening’ within a broader field of presence.

Figure 3. Myth Map of Stanton Drew (Author's own, 2025).

Walking with Stones

As I engaged with the stone circles, my movement changed, becoming orbital. I began walking in circular patterns, mirroring the stones' arrangement as if under their instruction. In this motion, I sensed that the stones

could remember, not metaphorically, but through a felt awareness of their capacity to retain and communicate presence via material form and human spatial alignment. During this period of the walk, my experience transitioned into what I can only describe as animistic, aligning with Marisol de la Cadena's (2015) notion of "Earth Beings", entities that resist classification within a purely modern ontology and instead assert other than-human modes of knowing and relating. Rather than viewing the stones as inert archaeological objects, they became co-participants, capable of holding and transmitting memory, even if not in a form legible to Western epistemologies. Listening, expanded beyond the auditory into a form of attentiveness that included felt textures (Hurcome, 2007), absences, and the thickening of time. This engagement shaped the myth map itself, which was less a representation of space than a composition of relation - an attempt to trace presences and resonances that elude conventional mapping: the liveliness of matter and the co-presence of human and more-than-human affect. In visual terms, this co-presence was expressed through blue human figures (*Fig 3*), chosen to show their permeability or translucence, as bodies between worlds.

Critical Analysis

The emergence of the blue beings within my myth map was not the product of creative whim, but a relational outcome of engaging with the site through *soft phenomenology*. It was through the spatial choreography of the visible stones, the buried concentric rings revealed by magnetometry, and the speculative presence of timber posts in digital reconstructions that these presences of the more-than-human seemed to arise. Rather than viewing the myth map as a subjective projection, I understand it as an interpretive synthesis, a way of acknowledging how certain configurations of matter, space, and movement can invite other-than-human copresences. My perspective aligns closely with Bishop's (2018) notion of *thresholding*, where art and perception are shaped through relational and affective encounters exceeding human intentionality. In this sense, the stones did not simply mark space; they animated it, drawing my attention toward what could be understood as an ontological opening (de la Cadena, 2015).

While the myth map was shaped by my own embodied encounters, it was not created in isolation. Local narratives, particularly the legend of the Devil's Fiddler, subtly informed how I perceived the site's temporal and affective thresholds that, upon reaching the stone circles, began to pulse with sonic, ritual imaginaries. On a separate visit, a local couple advised me not to remain inside the Great Circle for too long, referencing its biological or purgative effects. Though I did not set out to follow this guidance, I now reflect on whether this advice, perhaps remaining within my subconscious, played a part in my tendency to orbit the circles rather than enter inside them. My experience of Stanton Drew as a space of rhythm, ritual, and memory was shaped not only by walking and listening, but also by myths of the land. Such moments highlight how local knowledge, folklore, and informal encounters contribute to the affective atmosphere of a site, shaping how one moves through it. In this case, my actions were not guided solely by methodological intention, but by a

felt responsiveness to the landscape's social and sensory cues. Walking thus became more than observation, it became a mode of relating: a 'lifeworld practice' (Wunderlich, 2008).

This attunement to place also intersects with what Manning (2013) and Bergson (1990) describe as a more than-human relational milieu - a sensitivity to the movements, forces, and intensities that exceed the limits of conscious perception. By engaging with the sensorial, the myth map gave form to what might otherwise remain imperceptible. Rather than mapping fixed locations or visualising empirical data, it attempted to draw out the affective charge of the landscape, the way matter, memory, and myth coalesced in the body. Following Manning's (2013) claim that perception is not merely a faculty of representation but a threshold through which the world emerges, my engagement with Stanton Drew became less about interpreting the site and more about becoming-with it. In this sense, the myth map is not an appendage to fieldwork but an active participant in it, a visual and affective artefact of movements that cannot be fully articulated through conventional archaeological representations alone.

Conclusion

This project has explored Stanton Drew as a living composition of relations. Through an embodied, soft phenomenological approach, I sought to engage with the site not only through walking and observation, but through affective, relational modes of knowing. The myth map, rather than offering a conclusive interpretation, became a way of dwelling within the intensities of place, a means of tracing movements that exceed linear time, visual certainty, and human control. By drawing on more-than-human theory and engaging with the affective dimensions of archaeological landscapes, this project contributes to an ongoing shift in spatial practice, one that moves beyond representation and towards relational attunement. In doing so, it asks how we might listen differently, walk more attentively, and open ourselves to presences that are not easily categorised but no less real. At Stanton Drew, what emerged was not only a deeper sense of place, but an invitation to stay with its thresholds, and move with its rhythms, rather than impose our own.

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